

Reading of Draupadi as ‘The Celestial Astra, the Feminist Weapon Invoked with Special Chants’ in Chitra Banerjee’s *the Palace of Illusion*

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Dr.Mrs.G.Beulah, M.A., M.Phil., Ph.D.,

*Sri Meenakshi Government Arts College for Women (A)
Madurai, Tamil Nadu, South India*

Abstract

*Draupadi is the epitome of feminine excellence and the single representative of the entire novel *The Palace of Illusion*. Divakaruni makes Draupadi as the “Celestial astra, the weapons that must be invoked with special chants! They come from the Gods and return to them after being used. The most powerful ones can be used only once in a warrior’s lifetime.” She is used as a “Brahmastra” to destroy the evil things in the entire world. Because cleansing is the essential factor for the overall social change. Here Draupadi also “ascends the pyre” not to die but to live with her husband with the purity of heart, mind and soul. Fire cleanses her physically, emotionally, and mentally to start a fresh life with her husbands. A woman could create the kind of transnationalism in her own country with her binary efforts discarding the power and the western ways of Eurocentric dominance. She is the combination of all five elements so as to live with all the five husbands representing all the five elements. She becomes the atma of all the five husbands who represent the five elements.*

Keywords: Celestial astra, Brahmastra, pyre, transnationalism, chants, atma.

Introduction

The representative of the South-Asian immigrants, the multifaceted personality Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni has been recognized with “The American Book Award” for her short story collection *Arranged Marriage: Stories*. An Indian-American author published *The Palace of Illusion* through the eye of Draupadi from the Indian epic *Mahabharata* highlighting the age old struggle for power between the sons of Pandu and Dhristarashtra where men dominate the entire orbit with female helpers (wives). Despite the core theme of struggle, Divakaruni spreads a red carpet for the feministic excellence in Draupadi as she narrates the entire story from her winning point of view.

According to mythological stories, Draupadi is the incarnation of five women, representing all five elements, a rare combination to be seen in a single woman. Divakaruni shows Draupadi as the epitome of feminine excellence and the single representative of the

entire novel *The Palace of Illusion*. She is the Princess of Mahabharata with an unbending will, not born of woman, but from fire (agni), an enigmatic woman, the daughter of Drupad, the King of Panchaala, and above all the incarnation of Kali, the powerful deity to destroy evil. Draupadi was an unexpected gift to Drupad while he was expecting a son to take revenge on his enemy Drona.

Discussion

The words “diaspora,” “otherness,” “postcolonialism,” and “displacements” are the synonyms and self orientation of a feminine gender. Feminism talks of the establishments, and the social equality given to the women on par with men in the society. It may be a range of political propaganda but it is an ideology to be carried out equality to share a common goal and the equality of sexes. This may lead to establish educational and professional opportunities for women to have equal opportunities like men. Gayathri Spivak’s *Can the Subaltern Speak?* becomes a great challenge to be answered by the so called scholars with their great mastery over the colonial domination.

Spivak points out ‘sati’ which was at practice among the Hindus: “The Hindu widow ascends the pyre of the dead husband and immolates upon it. This is widow sacrifice (33).” Thereby the Europeans stopped that practice so as to show that the Indians are barbarians and the British are civilized by saving the “brown women from brown men” and constructed the identity over Indians. Spivak brings the suicide of Bhubaneswari Bhaduri which was misinterpreted by her family as an outcome of love failure rather than a protest. This subaltern can never speak as she is not alive to defend her case. Divakaruni makes Draupadi as the “Celestial astra, the weapons that must be invoked with special chants! They come from the Gods and return to them after being used. The most powerful ones can be used only once in a warrior’s lifetime (PI 28).” She is used as a “Brahmastra” to destroy the evil things in the entire world. Because cleansing is the essential factor for the overall social change.

Divakaruni strongly created her protagonist powerfully. Though a woman becomes an inferior being to undergo this kind of punishment, she has no chance to win her case. Here Draupadi also “ascends the pyre” not to die but to live with her husband with the purity of heart, mind and soul. Fire cleanses her physically, emotionally, and mentally to start a fresh life with her husbands. Draupadi’s conjugal life exhibits a spiritual contention over her five husbands with a tremendous self control. Honest relationship with faith and love could bring a greater change in the entirety. Draupadi was not given due respect as her brother. The plight of women in India is clearly given through the words of the tutor as he says “women were the root of all world’s troubles” (PI 24). This is the preconceived notion of the entire world of male domination. In the eyes of men, woman who gives birth to a new life becomes the root cause of all troubles in the world. The same tutor repeats “a kshatriya woman’s highest purpose in life is to support the warriors in her life: her father, brother, husband, and sons. If they should be called to war, she must be happy that they have the opportunity to fulfill a heroic destiny: (PI 25-26). What kind of juxtapositioning ideology is adopted to differentiate the gender discrimination, especially with women. Though the entire novel depicts the life history of Draupadi from birth to death in the first person narrative, Draupadi is very particular to fulfill the astonishing prophecy of her birth as she was emerging from the smoke there was the voice “behold we give you this girl, a gift beyond what you asked for. Take good care of her, for she will change the course of history” (PL 4-5).

In *Theorizing Diaspora: A Reader*, the term has been explained as a “journey across civilizations” and “this diasporic movement marks not a postmodern turn from history but a nomadic turn in which the very parameters of specific historical movements are embodied...scattered or regrouped into new points of becoming” (3). According to William Safran, the unique quality of the diaspora is that “they consider that they should, collectively, be committed to the safeguarding or re-

establishment of their authentic hometown and to its safety and richness” and in “constructing their communities” they become “independent centre of cultural creations; alternatively their creations continue to include convinced ethnosymbols, customs, and narratives of the homeland.” Draupadi’s role as a constructor of her community is specially designed after the deconstruction of the whole community with their “colonial domination of the other” as mentioned by Edward Said in *Orientalism*. Here Draupadi gives the solution that there is no need of European “civilizing mission” to make a new modern world as she could do away with the mythic visualization of predefined images of the savage people and lands beyond their imagination. A woman could create the kind of transnationalism in her own country with her binary efforts discarding the power and the western ways of Eurocentric dominance.

Draupadi keeps everything in her mind and waits for the right time to show her power and strength. She always ready to take up studies along with her brother. “A girl being taught what a boy was supposed to learn? Such a thing had never been heard of in the royal family of Panchal! Only when Krishna insisted that the prophecy” (PI 23) at her birth should come true to “get an education beyond what women were usually given” and it was the duty of the king to provide such education. So she “hungered to know about the amazing, mysterious world extended past (PI 23).” Her readiness to accept things with positivity for a transformation of the older order of savagery is very clear. She couldn’t accept the “blindfolded Gandhari” with her wifely virtue as she is “docile and overtly traditional” who has never expressed her opinions but “focused her entire attention on her blind husband’s needs” (PI 129). Dai ma also commented as “she’s dangerous with more power than most people realize, and one of these days she just might decide to use it” (PI 129). Draupadi has to tackle many people of her cadre like Gandhari, Sakuni, Duryodhan, and Dussanan. Though she is the princess of Hastinapur, the queen of the sons of Pandu she has been played upon by Yudhishtira at a game of dice with Duriyodhana, entrapping him to get Draupadi as his Dhasi.

Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni highlights the psychological sense of displacement subtly in *The Palace of Illusion* through Draupadi, as she had to move from Hastinapur. This is the second diasporic experience from her father to Hastinapur and from Hastinapur to an unknown place to live with her unknown husbands. “The chastised Dhritarashtra agreed to hand Yudhishtir his birthright” and “divide the kingdom in two... give the Pandavas the bigger half, leaving the smaller portion for his own son” (PI 137). But Draupadi could convert those diasporic experiences into finding a new world with new civilization by destroying the older form of ruling, socio-cultural set up, despair and disappointments, fundamentalism and revolutionary violence. She prepares herself as the sacrificing astra to set everything in the right order. She tries to fulfill the reason for her birth. She recounts the generational barrier of class discrimination and individual complexities with her first hand experiences. The problems of all diasporic women are identified with Draupadi with rootlessness, nostalgia, cultural assimilation, alienation, and identity crisis.

Summation

As Draupadi crossed the country along with her husbands, their vehicles “broke down on the poked and uneven road,” Krishna came for their rescue with soldiers, food, tents, and several sturdy horses (PI 137). The storyline drags while they construct a palace which Draupadi calls as “the Palace of Illusion” (PI 146). The palace has been constructed with stunning visual aesthetics which unravels a beautiful “Indra Prastha” as the “unparalleled grandeur of the Pandava Court” (PI 147). Now the orbit formed as “they were a unit together, five fingers that complemented each other to make up a powerful hand – a hand that would protect” (PI 148). Draupadi has the proud feeling that she is greater than the status of all the Pandavas because of her unique birth. She is the real chaste woman. She cleansed her body with fire after one year living with one husband. She is

the combination of all five elements so as to live with all the five husbands representing all the five elements. She becomes the atma of all the five husbands who represent the five elements. When Draupadi was so happy about her palace, Krishna advised her:

Don't be so attached to what is, after all, no more than stone and metal and asura sleight of hand. All things in this world change and pass away – some after many years, some overnight. Appreciate the Palace of Illusions, by all means. But if you identify so deeply with it, you set yourself up for sorrow (PI 149).”

Hence she is the celestial astra to be used once by the creator to create a new world with her profundity. Beyond all theories and 'isms' Draupadi is the first feminist in a real sense. Panchaali is the challenging female redefining the feministic perspective by removing all warriors, Gods, enemies, fateful events and ever manipulating male domination. Draupadi became the self created leader and saviour of her people through her power of feministic weapon. Draupadi a Celestial persona who is a creator and a creation with her feminine amalgamation imbued with her magical powers could create a new world and changed the course of history as prophesied earlier. She is not the destroyer but a constructor of a new order.

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